

The Impact and implications of Covid-19 on the relational, social, and healthcare experiences of Hospice care in the West Midlands (ICOH)

Knowledge Exchange Panel

26 May 2021

CONSENT to record the meeting

I agree
 I disagree

Overview

- **Part one:** Introductions
- **Part two:**
 - Recap – the study so far...
 - Format for the Knowledge Exchange Panel – Introducing the Modified Nominal Group Technique (M-NGT)

[BREAK]

- **Part three:** M-NGT
 - Round robin
 - Discussion
 - Shortlisting

[BREAK]

- **Part four:** Quick wins
- **Next steps...**

Introductions...

Smile for a photo!

Recap

- **Title:** The Impact and implications of Covid-19 on the relational, social, and healthcare experiences of Hospice care in the West Midlands (ICOH)
- **Study aim:** To identify nationally relevant recommendations to mitigate the uneven relational, social and healthcare impacts of Covid-19 upon hospice services for vulnerable service users and those that care for them.
- The **primary objectives** will seek to identify and act upon quick-win opportunities for the hospice community and so fulfil UKRI Agile Research and Innovation Response to Covid-19 criteria:
 1. What can we learn from the pandemic about the uneven relational, social and healthcare impacts of Covid-19 upon hospice services for vulnerable service users and those that care for them: (a) now / remaining pandemic; (b) future pandemics.
 2. What are the implications of the pandemic for future hospice care?
- The **secondary objectives** meet the criteria to "gather critical data and resources quickly for future research use".

Gantt chart:

Task / Month	1 April	2 May	3 June	4 July	5 Aug	6 Sept	7 Oct	8 Nov	9 Dec	10 Jan	11 Feb	12 Mar
Ethics (University BSREC)	Activity											
Knowledge Exchange Panel		Activity										
Evidence Notes		Output		Output		Output		Output		Output		
Interviews		a	a	b	b	c	c	d	d			
Knowledge Translation Workshops				a		b		c		d		
Cohort Reports					a		b		c		d	
Final Report												Output
Peer-reviewed papers (submitted)								j				ii
Presentations										Output	Output	Output

Key:

Activity	Activity
Output	Output

Study update:

- Study admin and governance
 - Ethics amendment (social media)
- Data collection
 - Grey evidence
 - Interviews (patient cohort)
- Conference abstracts
 - x3 submitted (MedSoc; AMPS; DDD15)

The Knowledge Exchange Panel

- Use our experiences and evidence collected so far as resources to **anticipate** and scope out the themes and issues for the four cohorts and reports.
 - Identify the **gaps** in our knowledge about the uneven relational, social and healthcare impacts of Covid-19 upon hospice services that this study can address.
- The goals of the Panel are:
 1. Identify and prioritise the themes, issues or questions to explore in the following ten months that will provide the greatest insight into the uneven relational, social and healthcare impacts of Covid-19 upon hospice services for service users and those that care for them.
 2. Identify any 'quick win' recommendations for policy or practice.

Introducing the Modified Nominal Group Technique (M-NGT)

Four stages:

1. Reflection (your preparation)
2. Round robin
3. Discussion
4. Shortlisting

Consensus Methods: Nominal Group Technique

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Karine Manera, Camilla S. Hanson, Talia Gutman, and Allison Tong

(2019) In P. Liamputtong (ed). *Handbook of Research Methods in Health Social Sciences*. Springer, 737-750.

Break?

Round robin

- Each person gets a chance to speak uninterrupted
- Reflect on themes suggested:
 - Are any issues or themes missing?
 - Do you have additional experience or evidence to add to a theme or issue?
 - Is there anything at this stage you think we should or should not prioritise? Can you say why?

Themes

- Place of palliative care / dying
- Changes to Service Delivery
- Bereavement and grief
- impact of pandemic on different groups
- Volunteers role
- quick adaptations due to COVID
- Mismatch of delivery Vs experiences
- Visiting hospices
- Training others (outreach?)
- Data collection and evaluation
- Staff resilience
- Use of tech
- Funding and resources

Discussion

Stage one

- Any questions, comments, follow-ups on anything a panel member has said?
 - Is there anything you agree or disagree with?
- Can we merge or group any themes together? Do any themes or issues need expanding or separating?

Stage two

- Is there anything at this stage we can agree on now that we should not prioritise for a particular cohort? Can you say why?
- Are there any themes you think we should look at? Why?

Identify and prioritise the themes, issues or questions to explore in the following ten months that will provide the greatest insight into the uneven relational, social and healthcare impacts of Covid-19 upon hospice services for service users and those that care for them.

Break?

(Take the time to consider your priority for each cohort)

Shortlisting

- Can we come to a consensus on any issue(s) for each cohort?

Alternatively

- Each participant provides a top three for each cohort.
- Discussion and consensus on top two or three issues for each cohort (voting if necessary).

*Identify and prioritise the themes, issues or questions to explore in the following ten months that will provide **the greatest insight into the uneven relational, social and healthcare impacts of Covid-19** upon hospice services for service users and those that care for them.*

Quick wins

- During the discussions, have you identified any 'quick win' recommendations for policy or practice?

Next steps...

- JM, AE, JF, CG will write-up outcomes with rationales and cross-referencing the evidence base.
- Share this with Marie Curie Policy Team to draft the Evidence Note.
 - Draft evidence note shared with all participants for comment.
- Publish the Evidence Note with support from Marie Curie PR & Comms week commencing **21 June 2021?**

- **Any questions or other business?**

